

LEXICAL AND STYLISTIC FEATURES OF ENGLISH RIDDLES

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Abstract

This study is devoted to the study of the lexical and stylistic features of English riddles. Every nation wants to tell the next generations their wisdom, teach them their accumulated experience, and also tell how their ancestors lived, what worries and joys they had, what this people has achieved and what glory it has among others. In this way, folk art was created, which since ancient times passed between people "from mouth to mouth", and was not recorded anywhere. The word "folklore" consists of two parts – folk "people" and lore "traditional knowledge", and itself means "folk wisdom". The authors of the article consider one of the independent genres of folklore – riddles.

Riddles have their own specific features and are strongly associated with human work. According to the traditional interpretation, riddles are mainly represented by six thematic blocks: classic riddles, ridiculous riddles, animal riddles, paradox riddles, letter riddles, number riddles.

The article presents examples proving the fact that English riddles are rich in terms of vocabulary used; the most frequently used semantic concepts were highlighted: animals; parts of the human body; terms from medicine; natural phenomena and weather; human creative activity; profession; names of countries, cities; writing.

The authors also highlight stylistic devices and artistic means of expression, widely represented in English riddles, including epithet, comparison, contrast, metaphor, personification, oxymoron.

As a result of the study ten main and largest thematic blocks were identified.

Keywords: English, linguistics, riddles, lexical features, stylistic features

1 INTRODUCTION

Every nation wants to impart its wisdom to the next generations, teach them the accumulated experience, and also tell them how their ancestors lived, what worries and joys they had, what this people achieved and what glory it has among others. Thus, folk art was created, which since ancient times passed between people "by word of mouth", and was not recorded anywhere. Many works of folklore had several variants, as each person could remake it in their own way. Later, with the invention of printing, folk art acquired a written form.

Riddles have their own specific features. At the same time, they are also classified as aphoristic genres of folk art, which also include proverbs and sayings. Riddles, proverbs and sayings have common features such as an artistic form and content, but the riddle still differs from the last two in special features.

Riddles are strongly connected with human labor activity and have attracted attention for centuries by the richness, intricacy and ingenuity of their content, the democratic essence of the ideas embedded in them, and the unexpected situations. "The term 'riddle' itself, – writes I.N. Tsallagova, "has an ancient origin. In the Old Russian language, the word "guessing" meant "to think", "to reflect", from these words the word "riddle" originated [Tsallagova, 2010].

A riddle is usually understood as a small folklore work constructed in the form of an allegory, containing an intricate question to which an exhaustive answer must be given" [Rosenbloom, 1976].

Archer Taylor, an American paremiologist, played an important role in the history of the study of English riddles. He was president of the American Folklore Society (1936-1937), a member of the London and Irish Folklore Societies (London Folklore Society, Folklore of Ireland Society), and editor of the Journal of American Folklore (Journal of American Folklore). In 1939, his book "A Bibliography of Riddles" was published.

A. Taylor gives the following definition of a riddle: "a true riddle consists of two descriptions of an object, metaphorical (figurative) and literal, and confuses the listener, who makes attempts to identify an object whose means of description are contradictory" [Taylor, 2017].

2 METHODS

The purpose of this study is a lexical, stylistic and contextual analysis of English riddles, as well as the identification of the most frequently occurring topics in these riddles, confirmation of their semantic originality. To achieve this goal, the following methods were used: a descriptive method involving the generalization and classification of the analyzed material; a continuous sampling method for collecting empirical material; synthesis, which serves for the theoretical generalization of the results of this course work.

The empirical material of this study was 250 riddles from collections of domestic and foreign authors, as well as materials from the Internet. The total number of analyzed examples amounted to 225 units.

The theoretical basis of the research is the works of the following authors devoted to linguistics and linguistic culture: Will R. Raine (2015); Joseph Rosenbloom (1976); A. Kadyrova, O. Strelkova, A. Ibragimova, F. Rakhimullina (2020), Mubarakshina, A.A., & Abdrakhmanova, A.A. (2019).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The Stylistic Features of English Riddles

Over time, English riddles have undergone significant thematical changes. According to the traditional interpretation, riddles are mainly represented by six thematic blocks: classic riddles, ridiculous riddles, animal riddles, paradox riddles, letter riddles, number riddles.

The researchers confirm this classification with the following examples.

Classic riddles

1) The more it dries, the wetter it becomes. What is it?

Answer: A towel.

2) Why can't your nose be twelve inches long?

Answer: Because then it would be a foot.

3) All of Ann's pets are dogs except one, and all of her pets are cats except one. How many cats and dogs does Ann have in total?

Answer: Ann has one cat and one dog.

Ridiculous riddles

1) How can you tell when there is an elephant in your sandwich?

Answer: When you can't pick it up.

2) How do you prevent a summer cold?

Answer: Catch it in the winter.

3) What is a duck's favorite snack?

Answer: Quackers.

Animal riddles

1) What do you call a bird in winter?

Answer: A brrrd.

2) What animal is bad to play cards with?

Answer: A Cheetah.

3) Where do hamsters come from?

Answer: Hamsterdam.

Paradox riddles are built on an internal contradiction between a question and an answer (a guess). From Greek, "paradox" means an unexpected phenomenon, sharply contradicting common sense, at odds with conventional wisdom.

1) How long did the Hundred Years War last?

Answer: 116 years, from 1337 to 1453.

2) What has a big mouth and never speaks?

Answer: A jar.

3) What has many ears but cannot hear?

Answer: A cornfield.

As you can see, riddles are based on unusual comparisons: the guesses expected in line with common sense and generally accepted opinion turn out to be false, and the most unexpected, but the only true ones, are the right ones.

Riddles about letters or using letters can be funny, unexpected, require logical thinking, but they always have a letter element:

1) Why is the letter \D\ so aggravating?

Answer: Because it makes MamaD.

2) What starts with \T\, ends with \T\, and is full of \T\?

Answer: Teapot.

3) What letter travels the greatest distance?

Answer: The letter \D\ because it is at the end of the world.

Special attention should be paid to the fact that this type of riddles has a very ancient history. The **poetic form of the English riddle** became most popular in Victorian times. The riddle usually consisted of several rhyming lines. One of the words contained a letter in each line, that was included in the name of the answer. And the last line most of all suggested to the listeners what or who they were talking about, for example:

My first is in tea but not in leaf

My second is in teapot and also in teeth

My third is in caddy but not in cosy

My fourth is in cup but not in rosy

My fifth is in herbal and also in health

My sixth is in peppermint and always in wealth

My last is in drink, so what can I be?

I'm there in a classroom, do you listen to me?

Answer: Teacher.

The difference between letter riddles and number riddles lies only in the fact that in the second case, the mandatory attribute is numbers instead of letters:

1) Why is the number 9 like a peacock?

Answer: Because it is nothing without its tail.

2) If butter is 50 cents a pound in Chicago, what are windowpanes in Detroit?

Answer: Usually glass.

In some cases, numerals are omitted in the structure of number riddles. As the study shows, in such cases, either mathematical operations are implied (addition, subtraction, multiplication, and others), or the riddle is based on a comparison of geometric proportions (height, length, speed, etc.). For example:

1) I am tall when young and short when I am old. What am I?

Answer: A candle.

2) What is the largest fly swatter?

Answer: A baseball bat.

From the above, it can be concluded that among the English riddles there is a group of logical-semantic riddles, which includes number riddles and letter riddles. This type of riddles especially develops logic, contributes to the formation of a special type of thinking.

It is interesting to investigate not only the semantic originality of decoding of riddles, but also the lexical composition of the coded part.

According to the analysis, the following semantic concepts are most often used in modern English riddles: animals; parts of the human body; terms from medicine; natural phenomena and weather; human creative activity; profession; names of countries, cities; everything related to writing.

Let's take a look at the research material:

I. **Animals:**

What's green, but not a leaf; copies others, but is not a monkey?

Answer: A parrot.

II. **Parts of the human body:**

It can be cut and will grow back. Yet when you least expect it, it may disappear never to return.

Answer: Hair.

III. **Terms from medicine:**

Why is the dentist so unhappy while at work?

Answer: Because he is always looking down in the mouth.

IV. **Natural phenomena and weather:**

I whith bored silver shine,

What you see is none of mine.

First I show you but a quarter,

Like the bow that guards the Tartar;

Then the half, and then the whole,

Ever dancing round the pole;

And true it is, I chiefly owe

My beauty to the shades below.

Answer: The Moon.

V. Human creative activity:

It lives without a body, hears without ears, speaks without a mouth, and is born in air. What is it?

Answer: An echo.

VI. Profession:

What salesman has the slickest line?

Answer: A hair grease salesman.

VII. Names of countries:

A person living in New York can't be buried in Pennsylvania. Why?

Answer: You should never bury a person who is living.

VIII. Everything related to writing:

What is the beginning of eternity,

The end of time and space;

The beginning of every end

And the end of every place?

Answer: The letter E!

The logical-semantic connection between the encoded word (the main part of the riddle) and the decoding (guess) is quite clearly visible. However, it should be remembered that despite the fact that English riddles are divided into several thematic groups (riddles about animals, professions, letters, etc.), for the most part they are not part of oral folk art in the form of poetic works, but resemble humorous questions.

Let's consider a riddle about animals.

What animal uses a nutcracker?

Answer: A toothless squirrel!

In this case, the encoding of the hidden animal occurs according to its physical characteristics: the answer must be sought among animals that eat nuts. As you know, the most famous such animal is the squirrel. However, animals never use nutcrackers, based on which the guesser assumes that this tool means something figurative, metaphorical. The decoding shows that there is no metaphor, this is a toothless squirrel. Thus, thematically, the riddle belongs to the "animal riddles" type, but it has all the main features of a "kids riddles" type.

Let's consider the following riddle.

What do you call a frog with no legs?

Answer: Unhappy

In this case, the semantic connection of words in encoding and decoding is obvious. The key word in the main part of the riddle is a frog, whose characteristic feature is the ability to hop. The answer contains a word that semantically means "unable to jump" - unhappy. In this case, there are also signs of a humorous riddle and a prank riddle: unhappy is a modified word from "unhappy". Thus, a frog without legs cannot jump, and at the same time appears to be unhappy because of this.

Thus, it is necessary to confirm the fact that the peculiarity of the modern English riddle is its basis on a joke, prank joke or paradox, which has an absolute impact on the semantic connection between the code contained in the main part of the riddle and the decoding, that is, the answer. To trace the semantic connection between the code and its decoding, it is often necessary to build a special logical chain, and in some cases, break the phraseological unit given in the code into separate lexical units.

3.1 The stylistic features of English riddles

Stylistically, English riddles are characterized by a variety of artistic means: comparisons, contrasts, metaphors, epithets, personifications.

Based on whether words in a figurative sense are used in the coding part of the text or not, riddles can be descriptive or metaphorical. Descriptive riddles can characterize an image, object or phenomenon through actions. For example:

1) *Four jolly men sat down to play;*

And played all night till break of day;

They played for money and not for fun,

With separate scores for everyone.

Yet when they came to square accounts,

They all had made quite fair amounts!

Can you the paradox explain?

If no one lost, how could all gain?

Answer: The Four men were musicians. After the performance they were all paid.

2) *In spring you're glad to see me,*

In summer I help you cool,

In autumn I give you food,

In winter I make you warm

Answer: An apple-tree.

The next riddle is based on contrast "day"- "night", "blue"- "white":

It's blue by night,

By day it's white.

It is cold and not dry,

It falls from the sky

Answer: Snow.

The guessed word is often characterized through certain qualities, for example, color:

Clean, but not water,

White, but not snow,

Sweet, but not ice-cream,

What is it?

Answer: Sugar.

Actions and signs in the description can be combined:

I'll keep your hair dry.

Bring me just in case.

I'm long and light to carry.

Don't open me in the house.

I hope you don't need me today.

Answer: Umbrella.

Personification is the most common technique in English riddles. Musical instruments are endowed with human abilities:

What did the guitar say to the rock star?

Answer: Quit picking on me!

However, most often representatives of the animal world are endowed with human qualities. For example:

1) *What do you call a grumpy cow?*

Answer: Moody.

2) *What did the hotel manager say to the elephant who couldn't pay his bill?*

Answer: Pack your trunk and clear out.

3) *Do skunks celebrate Valentine's Day?*

Answer: Sure, they're very scent-mental!

The structural feature of the English riddle as a humorous question has been mentioned. It is quite natural that it is mainly superfeatures, superpowers that can motivate someone to solve a riddle. This explains the frequency of use of superlative adjectives in such riddles, which is formed using the suffix -est added to the adjective in the positive degree or through the auxiliary word "the most":

1) *Which kind of nuts are the softest nuts?*

Answer: Donuts.

2) *What part of your body has the most rhythm?*

Answer: Your eardrums.

Metaphors are often found in riddles:

There is something that is nothing, but it has name. It joins our walks; it joins our talks; it plays in every game? What is it?

Answer: Your shadow.

Some riddles are based on antonyms. The function of opposites in riddles is used for a wide variety of purposes. Thus, the following riddles are based on antonyms expressing different directions of actions, signs, and social phenomena:

What goes up and never comes down?

Answer: Your age.

What is the difference between here and there?

Answer: The letter "T".

What is the difference between a hill and a pill?

Answer: A hill is hard to go up and a pill is hard to get down.

An oxymoron, combining incompatible things, functions as part of a riddle as a way of creating humor, jokes or irony:

1) *Why is poison so tasty?*

Answer: Because it's delicious poison.

2) *What silence can speak?*

Answer: Speaking silence.

We have analyzed different thematic groups of English riddles and can draw the following conclusion: despite the fact that the modern English riddle is far from poetic, it is also characterized by the presence of a variety of artistic means: epithets, comparisons, contrasts, metaphors, personifications, oxymorons.

4 SUMMARY

Thus, after analyzing the entire set of riddles taken as research material, we can draw several conclusions.

First, English riddles are rich in terms of the vocabulary used – English riddles most often use the following semantic concepts: animals; parts of the human body; terms from medicine; natural phenomena and weather; creative activity of a person; profession; names of countries, cities; everything related to writing.

Secondly, English riddles present a significant number of stylistic techniques and artistic means, such as epithets, comparison, opposition, metaphor, illustration, oxymoron.

Third, in the course of the study, ten main and largest thematic blocks were identified, such as riddles about animals (32 riddles); riddles about professions (27 riddles); riddles about the structure of the human body (17 riddles); riddles from the field of everyday life (16 riddles); riddles about weather, natural phenomena (20 riddles); riddles about heritage, value attitudes and Culture (24 riddles); riddles about clothing items (4 riddles); riddles about food (13 riddles); riddles about plants (6 riddles); riddles about sports (31 riddles). Thus, after analyzing the entire set of riddles taken as research material, we can draw several conclusions.

5 CONCLUSION

English riddles are a complex phenomenon from the point of view of linguistics (especially semantics). Their functional, thematic, and lexical features are unique.

The uniqueness lies in the ability to represent the cultural characteristics of the linguistic and cultural community to which they belong. For example, the English riddle is characterized by an appeal to national heritage (the use of native English proverbs and sayings). This is more evident in the ability to encode concepts. Also unique is the typical structure of English riddles and the constant use of humor.

It was on the material of riddles that many artistic principles were formed, she seemed to be the progenitor of such literary concepts as oxymoron, personification, metaphor.

The main goal set out in the introduction has been achieved. The tasks outlined there have been largely fulfilled, but the structural and conceptual features can be worked out in more detail. It is also worth considering that when expanding the analyzed material, any other important linguistic and semiotic aspects may be revealed.

The whole world began with a riddle, as indicated by a large number of biblical motifs of English puzzles. That is why the study of such an important cultural and linguistic phenomenon is very important.

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